

Adam Smith, Free Trade and the Origin of Customs Unions

Matthias Klaes, University of Dundee & DMKA Services

v2.6, 4 Nov 2025, SES 2026 Glasgow

Extended Abstract

Keywords:

Economic History; Adam Smith; Friedrich List; German Customs Union; Free Trade; Economic Methodology; Transaction Costs

JEL: N7, B1, B4

Adam Smith's *Wealth of Nations* (1776) will mark its 250th anniversary in 2026. This jubilee coincides with a period of considerable geopolitical uncertainty relating to one of the central tenets of Smith's foundational treatise: the doctrine of free trade. Thirty years after the establishment of the World Trade Organisation and the heydays of an US led Washington consensus, the main cheerleader of that consensus has begun embracing trade policy as a unilateral tool of choice, strictly subordinate to wider geostrategic goals (Navarro 2025a, b). This policy shift has drawn fresh attention to the policy implications of Smith's analysis of free trade.

The present paper responds to this renewed interest in the case for free trade that Smith presented in the *Wealth of Nations* by seeking to contribute to recent debates in the methodology of economic policy advice (Boldyrev and Sent 2025). Smith's ideas had a profound impact on 19th century British trade policy, but they were also taken up across most of post-Napoleonic continental Europe. Focusing on the reception of Smith's ideas in the German states in particular, the paper presents a comparative analysis of the main vectors of influence of the reception of the *Wealth of Nations* in those states. This will allow a close look at the role of free trade ideas in the positioning of particular tariff and other trade policies around the strategic pursuit by Prussia of the establishment and rapid expansion of the German customs union during the first half of the 19th century.

The economic and wider historical developments leading up to Bismarck's Reich are relatively well understood, as is the history of Smith's concept of free trade. What has received less attention is how the spread of free trade ideas intersected with contemporary policy debates and influenced how policy makers shaped the detail of specific trade policies during those years. As a key finding, the paper will demonstrate how both proponents and critics of free trade were able to draw on the *Wealth of Nations* as an inspiration for and defence of their conflicting positions, with important insights relating to the anchoring role of economic concepts in wider public debate.

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